

Observing Others Eat Influences Attitudes Toward Insect-Based Foods

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Abstract

Insect-based foods represent a sustainable and ethical alternative protein, but their adoption in Western societies faces cultural resistance due to disgust and unfamiliarity. We examined the effectiveness of two social learning strategies, Observational Evaluative Conditioning (observing others' emotional reactions) and Vicarious Consumption (observing others eating), for shaping attitudes and behavioral intentions toward insect-based biscuits. Experiment 1 ($N = 131$) tested only Observational Evaluative Conditioning, and it influenced spontaneous preferences and intentions for both insect-based and regular biscuits. Experiment 2 ($N = 293$) examined Observational Evaluative Conditioning and Vicarious Consumption. Both strategies improved attitudes toward insect-based foods compared to baseline, with no significant difference between them. These findings suggest that observing others' consumption and emotional reactions can reduce aversion to insect-based products. Observational Evaluative Conditioning and Vicarious Consumption offer promising, scalable approaches to promote acceptance of novel, eco-friendly foods, potentially facilitating sustainable dietary shifts without requiring direct exposure or taste experience.

Keywords: Social Influence; Modeling; Consumer Perception; Social Learning; Observational Evaluative Conditioning

Introduction

As the global population grows, the resulting strain on agricultural systems has intensified the search for sustainable protein sources. Insects have emerged as a promising solution, offering a nutritionally rich alternative that is high in essential nutrients (Van Huis et al., 2013; Van Huis, 2022). Insect farming is also environmentally advantageous, producing lower greenhouse gas emissions and requiring less land than conventional livestock production (Ooninx & de Boer, 2012; Van Huis & Rumpold, 2023). Ethically, insects may represent a preferable option, as their simpler nervous systems suggest a much lower capacity for suffering compared to vertebrates (Adamo, 2016; Burrell, 2017; Delvendahl et al., 2022; Gibbons et al., 2022). Thus, encouraging even a partial substitution of meat with insect-based foods could reduce overall animal suffering, particularly as welfare-oriented rearing and slaughter protocols continue to evolve. Despite these nutritional, environmental, and ethical advantages, Western societies remain resistant to consuming insects. Unlike foods that are disliked, such as certain vegetables, or those that are culturally specific, like black pudding, the resistance to insects is rooted in a fundamental perception: Insects are not seen as food at all, but rather are associated with dirt or contamination (Deroy, Reade, & Spence, 2015; Fasanelli et al., 2020; Kröger et al., 2022). This deeply ingrained perception creates a significant barrier to acceptance.

On the other hand, in many non-Western societies, insects are commonly consumed as part of the diet, and archaeological evidence suggests that they were a significant food source for early humans (Van Huis et al., 2022; Van Huis & Rumpold, 2023). This contrast highlights the role of cultural influences in shaping dietary preferences (Jeong & Lee, 2021) and suggests that Western aversion to insect-based food is learned rather than universal. Accordingly, social learning interventions may offer a promising route to changing evaluations and increasing willingness to consume insect-based foods. Most previous interventions aimed at improving Western consumers' reactions to insect food have relied on information-based approaches, such as emphasizing the health and environmental benefits of insect-based foods (Laureati et al., 2024; van Huis & Rumpold, 2023). Although these strategies can raise awareness, they seldom alter persistent disgust or perceptions that insects are not food. By contrast, interventions that highlight similarities between insect-based food and familiar foods (Fedeli et al., 2025) or that employ social learning strategies (Fedeli et al., 2024)

appear promising for reducing avoidance. While information alone does not disrupt underlying disgust and neophobic reactions (i.e., fear of new foods), cognitive techniques that engage mental representations of insect-food, encourage comparisons, or utilize observational learning may more effectively address the sources of rejection. Therefore, when designing interventions to promote acceptance of novel foods, cognitive strategies should be prioritized over simple information delivery, as the latter often fails to challenge deeply held rejection schemas and food norms. Here, we will focus specifically on social learning strategies.

Using social learning strategies to overcome negative reactions to food with insect derivatives.

In Western cultures, people rarely observe others (i.e., social models) eating insect-based foods, which may contribute to the persistence of negative attitudes toward such foods. By contrast, observing others' eating behavior has a powerful effect on individuals' eating choices with traditional foods (Cruwys et al., 2015). In social modeling of food choices, two aspects of the model's behavior can be distinguished: the act of consuming the food and the emotional response displayed by the model.

Vicarious Consumption

Observing another person (the model) consume a food can shape one's evaluation. Reviews by Cruwys and colleagues (2015) and Suwalska and Bogdański (2021) show that social modeling reliably affects choices and behaviors, particularly for highly palatable, high-calorie foods such as snacks, chocolate, and ice cream. When, more rarely, less appealing foods, such as carrots or cucumbers, are examined, effects tend to be smaller and may require repeated exposure. Thus, although social modeling is a robust mechanism, its impact appears reduced for foods that are initially unattractive. This limitation may be even more pronounced for insect-based foods. Nonetheless, research using a vicarious approach paradigm indicates that merely learning that someone has approached rather than avoided an insect-based food can create a preference (Fedeli et al., 2024), suggesting that observing consumption alone may be sufficient to nudge attitudes even toward culturally resisted foods.

From a theoretical perspective, witnessing a model consume a target food can foster positive attitudes, a vicarious consumption (VC) effect, for multiple reasons. First, the act of eating is itself

evaluated positively (Zogmaister, Brignoli, et al., 2023). Therefore, observing someone eat can produce evaluative conditioning (Moran et al., 2023), with the food as the conditioned stimulus and eating as a positive unconditioned stimulus. Second, from a propositional perspective (De Houwer, 2018), observers may infer that, if someone eats a food, they like it, and therefore the food must be good (see Zogmaister, Brignoli, et al., 2023, for a related discussion).

Observational Evaluative Conditioning

Models can go beyond merely demonstrating consumption by also conveying their appreciation or dislike of a food. Adding this evaluative information may strengthen social modeling effects and thus represent a particularly effective strategy for improving reactions to insect-based foods.

Various studies have examined the effects of models' positive or negative emotional expressions during food consumption (Baeyens et al., 1996, 2001; Barthomeuf et al., 2012; Cruwis et al., 2015; Suwalska et al., 2021). Most research has focused on appetitive or neutral foods and shows that observing a model consume a food and express an appreciation typically increases subsequent liking for that food (e.g., Kasran et al., 2022, 2023). This effect is known as Observational Evaluative Conditioning (OEC; Baeyens et al., 1996; Mineka et al., 1984). Evidence for OEC with commonly unappealing foods, such as Brussels sprouts or black pudding, is more limited and mixed: Negative expressions reliably reduce liking, whereas positive expressions sometimes fail to increase it (Barthomeuf et al., 2009; Edwards et al., 2022, 2024; Soussignan et al., 2015).

Within an associative theoretical framework (Conditioning Hypothesis, Baeyens et al., 2001), the model's emotional reaction functions as an unconditioned stimulus that elicits a corresponding evaluative response in the observer. When the food (conditioned stimulus) is paired with this reaction, associations form between their mental representations, allowing the food to elicit a similar response later on. By contrast, the inferential account suggests that observers derive the evaluative qualities of a stimulus by interpreting the model's reaction (De Houwer et al., 2021), for instance inferring that a food is good because the model appears to like it.

The Present Research

We examined the effects of Observational Evaluative Conditioning (OEC) and Vicarious Consumption (VC) on attitudes toward insect-based foods across two experiments. We began with OEC because, of the two social learning strategies, it was expected to be the most effective. OEC combines the observation of consumption with the model's affective reaction, whereas VC involves observing consumption without emotional cues.

Experiment 1 focused on OEC. Participants were randomly assigned to one of two between-participant conditions: regular biscuits, to validate the paradigm with conventional stimuli, or insect-based biscuits, to test whether OEC generalizes to culturally resisted foods. In both conditions, the model consumed two brands and expressed a positive reaction to one and a negative reaction to the other.

After establishing the efficacy of this full social learning signal, Experiment 2 tested whether observation of consumption alone (VC) would also influence preferences and evaluations. This experiment included three between-participant levels: baseline, VC, and OEC. To align with the goal of improving attitudes, the OEC condition included only a positive model reaction (OEC+). Experiment 2 also shifted from an intra-category to an inter-category comparison, examining whether VC and OEC+ could alter preferences between biscuits with and without insect ingredients. This design enabled us to test whether social modeling can enhance evaluations of insect-based foods compared to non-insect alternatives and whether affective reactions are necessary for such effects.

Overall, this research addresses a largely neglected domain by examining OEC and VC with foods that are typically perceived as unappealing or culturally resisted. Prior research on VC and OEC focused mainly on palatable or neutral foods (Baeyens et al., 1996, 2001; Barthomeuf et al., 2012; Cruwys et al., 2015; Kasran et al., 2022, 2023; Suwalska & Bogdański, 2021), with studies on disliked foods showing weaker or inconsistent effects (Barthomeuf et al., 2009; Edwards et al., 2022, 2024; Soussignan et al., 2015). By examining insect-based foods, the present studies offer valuable information on the effectiveness of these strategies with this type of stimuli. Moreover, it sheds light on the role of positive affective reactions as a means for changing attitudes by directly comparing within the same experiment the effects of procedures with and without those reactions. Practically, the findings from this research could have implications beyond those for communication strategies

regarding insect-based foods and approaches to persuade consumers. If proven effective with insect-containing foods, the OEC or VC strategy could also be applied to interventions aimed at encouraging people to adopt other potentially beneficial dietary behaviors.

In addition to standard direct measures, we employed indirect measures to assess spontaneous and automatic reactions toward insect-based foods. Such approaches are rare in research on novel food interventions (e.g., Fedeli et al., 2024, 2025; Verneau et al., 2016), but are crucial because, as highlighted by Brunner and colleagues (2025), indirect assessment techniques can capture aspects of consumer attitudes that self-report measures might miss, offering a more complete picture of intervention effectiveness.

Open science practices

Both experiments were preregistered (Experiment 1, <https://osf.io/exb82>; Experiment 2, <https://osf.io/gzh5a>) prior to data collection, with any deviations from preregistrations clearly indicated. The materials, data, and analysis syntax are openly available and can be accessed at the following links: <https://osf.io/7j8vf> (Experiment 1) and <https://osf.io/erpkm/> (Experiment 2).

We clearly differentiate between preregistered and exploratory analyses.

Experiment 1

Overview

Following Kasran and colleagues (2023), participants watched short video clips depicting a model tasting two brands of sweet biscuits. After sampling one brand, the model displayed a facial expression of appreciation; after the other, the model expressed disgust. We then measured participants' spontaneous evaluative reactions and behavioral intentions toward each brand. Half of the participants observed the model consuming insect-based biscuits, and the other half viewed the model eating traditional biscuits. This design enables testing the effectiveness of OEC with insect-based foods while confirming that the strategy operates as expected in our setting using conventional biscuits, establishing a baseline to distinguish effects of the target food from characteristics of the materials or procedure.

Participants and design

The experiment employed a mixed 2 x 2 design: biscuit type (regular vs. insect biscuits; between participants) x reaction (appreciation vs. disgust; within participants). A total of 163 participants (97 women, 60 men, six non-binary; $M_{age} = 24.93$ years, $SD = 6.06$) volunteered for the study. Participants were recruited via the Departmental Subject Management Pool, where they received study information and registered to participate, and through word of mouth. Those recruited from the Management Pool earned CFUs proportional to their time commitment; no additional compensation was provided. A power analysis using G*Power 3 (Faul et al., 2007), with $\alpha = .017$ (Bonferroni criterion for three dependent variables), power $(1 - \beta) = .90$, and an effect size of $f = 0.25$, to test H1 and H2 (described below) using a 2 x 2 mixed model ANOVA indicated a required total sample size of $N = 112$. Anticipating a low or null correlation between within-participant measures, we conservatively set $r = 0$. Due to online data collection, recruitment could not be stopped precisely at this target.

After applying preregistered exclusion criteria (see below), data from 132 participants were analyzed, with 68 in the regular biscuit condition and 64 in the insect biscuits condition. For each brand, we measured three dependent variables: spontaneous affective reactions, self-reported attitudes, and behavioral intentions.

Materials

Target products. We used two biscuit brands: an existing, relatively uncommon commercial brand, which we refer to as Darivo in this article to protect the interest of the brand; and Medeva, a mock brand created for the study. The mock brand was designed to resemble the existing brand in length, Italian-sounding character, and three-syllable structure. The identity of the commercial brand corresponding to Darivo is available upon request for exact replication. For each brand, we produced five images showing the brand, its packaging, or both. The image sets were carefully matched: For every image of one brand, a corresponding image of the other brand was created with the same general characteristics (e.g., if one image showed two packages, the parallel image depicted two packages of the other brand).

Videos. The two biscuit brands served as conditioned stimuli. Each brand was presented in a 15-second video, beginning with a three-second display of the biscuit package. The brand name was clearly visible, and in the insect condition, the presence of insect powder was explicitly indicated. A male model then took a biscuit from the package, tasted it, and displayed either appreciation or disgust, accompanied by a sound consistent with the emotional reaction. The specific emotion displayed for each brand was counterbalanced between participants. The model, a young Caucasian man, stood in front of an Italian theme park, with the park's name visible in the background to indicate the scene was filmed in Italy.

Manipulation check. After viewing the videos, participants answered two questions regarding the model's reactions to each biscuit brand: "What expression did the boy show after tasting the biscuit?" Response options were: Satisfied, Disgusted, No particular expression, or I do not remember. If participants answered incorrectly or indicated they did not remember, the videos were shown again.

Brief Implicit Association Tests (BIAT). The task was implemented following Sriram and Greenwald (2009; Experiments 1 and 2) and run in Qualtrics using the procedure described by Maimon (2020). The two biscuit brands were target categories, with five images per brand. Positive and negative taste-related adjectives served as attribute categories: tasty, good, appetizing, enticing, and appealing for Positive; disgusting, nasty, nauseating, repulsive, and vomiting for Negative. Attribute assignment was counterbalanced, with half of the participants first categorizing the brand with positive adjectives, while the other half categorized it first with negative ones. Participants completed two consecutive BIATs, one per brand, each comprising two training blocks (1 and 3) of 8 trials and two critical blocks (2 and 4) of 32 trials. Stimuli were presented in random order, with images on odd trials and adjectives on even trials. BIAT order was counterbalanced across participants. The BIAT had a built-in penalty: incorrect responses required participants to provide the correct answer before continuing, with response latencies recorded on the correct response.

Self-reported attitudes. Participants completed two semantic differentials, one per brand, using the same adjectives as in the BIAT paired as follows: Tasty–Disgusting, Good–Nasty, Appetizing–Nauseating, Enticing–Repulsive, and Appealing–Retching. Ratings were on a 7-point

scale. Due to a programming error, data from the semantic differential scales were not successfully recorded and are unavailable for analysis.

Intentions. Four items assessed the intention to purchase and consume insect-based foods:

1. If they are available in the shops I usually visit, I will probably buy them.
2. I am going to buy them no matter where they are sold.
3. As soon as I can, I am going to eat them.
4. If they are offered to me, I will probably taste them.

Participants responded on a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = *strongly disagree*, 2 = *disagree*, 3 = *neither agree nor disagree*, 4 = *agree*, 5 = *strongly agree*.

Knowledge of brands. Prior knowledge of the biscuit brands was assessed with the question: “Have you ever heard of this brand before this experiment?” Response options were: “No, I have never heard of it,” “Yes, I have heard of it, but I do not know what it is,” and an open-ended option “Yes, I know it, and I am familiar with what it is (please specify).”

Disgust and interest toward eating insects. These were measured using eight items from the Entomophagy Attitude Questionnaire (EAQ; La Barbera et al., 2020), comprising the Disgust and Interest subscales. Participants rated each item on a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = *not at all*, 2 = *a little*, 3 = *moderately*, 4 = *a lot*, 5 = *very much*.

Self-Reported Single-Item “Use Me” question (SRSI; Meade & Craig, 2012). Participants indicated whether their data should be included in our analyses (No/Yes).

Demographic questions. Participants reported age, gender, Italian proficiency, dietary type (omnivorous, vegetarian, vegan, or other), and student status.

Procedure

The experiment was programmed in Inquisit 6.6.1 and administered online via Inquisit Web (Millisecond Software). After providing informed consent, participants were informed they would watch short videos about two biscuit brands. Following Kasran and colleagues (2022, Experiment 1), each participant viewed the two videos – one per brand – three times each, in a random sequence. Brand-valence pairings were counterbalanced across participants: one brand was paired with the positive reaction, and the other with the negative reaction. After viewing the videos, participants

completed the manipulation check. If responses were incorrect for either brand, the videos were replayed until correct, with a maximum of four attempts. Participants then completed the BIAT, the semantic differential, and the intention-to-buy-and-eat scales. Semantic differentials always preceded intention questions and the order of BIATs and self-reports was counterbalanced between participants. Measures of prior brand knowledge, disgust, and interest in eating insect followed. Participants then completed the SRSI “Use Me” item to identify careless responding and provided demographic information.

Primary Hypotheses

Building on research on Observational Evaluative Conditioning and Vicarious Consumption, and considering that prior studies report stronger conditioning effects for neutral or positively valenced foods than for initially disliked foods (Barthomeuf et al., 2009; Edwards et al., 2022, 2024; Soussignan et al., 2015; Moran et al., 2025), we formulated the following hypotheses:

H1) Participants will prefer the brand associated with appreciation over the brand associated with disgust across all three measures (BIAT, semantic differential, intention).

H2) This preference will be stronger for regular biscuits than for insect-based biscuits.

Secondary Hypotheses

Although H2 hypothesized an attenuated effect for insect-based biscuits, we expected the OEC effect to remain detectable within each food category, yielding the following hypotheses:

H3) Participants viewing videos featuring regular biscuits will prefer the brand associated with appreciation over the brand associated with disgust, replicating Kasran et al. (2023).

H4) Participants viewing videos featuring insect-based biscuits will also prefer the brand associated with appreciation over the brand associated with disgust, extending those findings.

Results

Due to a programming error, semantic differential responses were not recorded.

Consequently, all hypothesis tests rely on indirect measures of attitudes and self reported behavioral intentions. Statistical analyses were performed in R (R Core Team, 2023). Using the following packages: readr (Wickham, Hester & Bryan, 2024), dplyr (Wickham et al., 2023), tidyr (Wickham, Vaughan & Girlich, 2024), reshape2 (Wickham, 2007), ez (Lawrence, 2016), effectsize (Ben-Shachar,

Lüdecke & Makowski, 2020), psych (Revelle, 2025), car (Fox & Weisberg, 2019), apaTables (Stanley, 2021), purrr (Wickham & Henry, 2025), and MBESS (Kelley, 2025).

Preliminary analyses

Data from participants who answered ‘No’ to the SRSI question ($n = 5$), were vegetarians ($n = 7$) or vegans ($n = 3$), scored below 75% correct responses on either BIAT ($n = 16$), or reported prior knowledge of the Darivo brand ($n = 0$) were excluded, following preregistration. The final sample comprised 132 participants (regular biscuits: $n = 68$; insect-containing biscuits: $n = 64$). Potential outliers were screened using the 3-MAD rule and visual inspection; no outliers were detected.

BIAT scores for each brand were computed separately using the D measure (Greenwald, Nosek, & Banaji, 2003). This computation was based on the difference between the mean penalized latency in blocks pairing the brand with negative words and the mean for blocks pairing it with positive words (see Zogmaister et al., 2025, for a similar approach). Higher scores indicate more positive attitude. Reliability was Cronbach’s $\alpha = .79$ (Darivo) and $\alpha = .83$ (Medeva) in the regular biscuit conditions, Cronbach’s $\alpha = .76$ (Darivo) and $\alpha = .82$ (Medeva) in the insect-based biscuit conditions. Scores were recoded to reflect the brand paired with the positive reaction versus the brand paired with the negative reaction, irrespective of the specific brand, so that the focus was on the effect of emotional reaction rather than brand identity.

Mean responses on the four-item intention scale were computed separately for Darivo ($\alpha = .82$ for the regular biscuit condition; $\alpha = .91$ for the insect-based biscuit condition) and Medeva ($\alpha = .86$ for regular biscuits; $\alpha = .87$ for insect-based biscuits). Higher values indicate stronger intentions to buy and eat the product. For analysis, we computed the difference between the mean score for the brand paired with the model’s positive reaction and the mean score for the brand paired with the negative reaction. Consequently, positive values reflect a preference for the brand associated with the positive reaction, whereas negative values indicate a preference for the brand associated with the negative reaction.

Mean scores were computed for the EAQ subscales: disgust (five items, $\alpha = .92$) and interest (three items, $\alpha = .91$). Higher scores indicate greater disgust or interest toward consuming insect-containing foods. Descriptive statistics and inter-measure correlations are reported in Table 1.

Note. Values in brackets represent 95% confidence intervals. † $p < .10$, * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Test of the Hypotheses

To test Hypotheses H1 and H2, we conducted two mixed-model ANOVAs with biscuit type (regular vs. insect-containing, between participants) and emotional reaction (appreciation-paired vs. disgust-paired, within participants) as factors, using BIAT and intention scores as dependent variables. To test H3 and H4, we next conducted paired sample t-tests for each biscuit type.

For BIAT scores, the mixed-model ANOVA revealed a significant main effect of emotional reaction, $F(1,130) = 36.82, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .221, 95\% \text{ CI } [.123, 1.000]$, with higher scores for the brand paired with appreciation ($M = 0.26, SD = 0.52$) than for the brand paired with disgust ($M = -0.15, SD = 0.55$), supporting H1. The main effect of biscuit type was not significant, $F(1,130) = 0.53, p = .466, \eta^2_p = .004, 95\% \text{ CI } [.000, 1.000]$, suggesting that insect ingredients did not influence automatic reactions. The reaction X biscuit type interaction was also non-significant, $F(1,130) = 0.65, p = .421, \eta^2_p = .005, 95\% \text{ CI } [.000, 1.000]$, indicating that emotional reaction effect on BIAT scores was similar for regular and insect-containing biscuits, contrary to H2.

Despite the non-significant interaction, preregistered paired-sample t-tests were conducted for each biscuit type to test hypotheses H3 and H4. BIAT scores were higher for the brand paired with appreciation than for the brand paired with disgust for both regular (H3) and insect-containing biscuits (H4). Table 2 reports the means, standard deviations, and t-test results by biscuit type and reaction.

For intention scores, the mixed-model ANOVA revealed a significant main effect of emotional reaction, $F(1,130) = 99.35, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .433, 95\% \text{ CI } [.333, 1.000]$, confirming H1. Participants reported greater intention to buy and consume biscuits paired with appreciation ($M = 3.35, SD = 0.90$) than with disgust ($M = 2.46, SD = 0.92$). Although the overall intention scores (calculated as the difference between positive- and negative-paired biscuits) were higher for regular biscuits ($M = 0.96, SD = 1.02$) than for insect-containing biscuits ($M = 0.81, SD = 1.02$), the main effect of biscuit type did not reach the preregistered significance level of $p < .025; F(1,130) = 4.15, p = .044, \eta^2_p = .031, 95\% \text{ CI } [.000, 1.000]$. The interaction between reaction and biscuit type was not significant, $F(1, 130) = 0.80, p = .373, \eta^2_p = .006, 95\% \text{ CI } [.000, 1.000]$, indicating that the OEC effect did not differ between biscuit types, and H2 was not supported.

Following preregistration, we tested H3 and H4 using paired-sample t-tests for each biscuit type. Consistent with prediction, the emotional reaction significantly influenced both conditions, with higher intention score for the brand paired with appreciation than with disgust. Table 2 presents the means, standard deviations, and t-test results by biscuit type and reaction.

Table 2.

Experiment 1: Mean BIAT and Intention Scores (SDs in Parentheses) by Biscuit Type and Model's Emotional Reaction.

	Positive reaction	Negative reaction	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	Cohen's <i>d</i>
<i>Regular biscuits (n = 68)</i>					
BIAT	0.21 (0.56)	-0.15 (0.55)	3.52	< .001	0.43 [0.18, .067]
Intentions	3.52 (0.70)	2.55 (0.91)	7.77	<.001	0.94 [0.65, 1.23]
<i>Biscuits with insects (n = 64)</i>					
BIAT	0.31 (0.47)	-0.15 (0.56)	5.24	< .001	0.65 [0.38, 0.92]
Intentions	3.17 (1.04)	2.37 (0.93)	6.34	< .001	0.79 [0.51, 1.07]

Note. Values in brackets represent 95% confidence intervals.

Ancillary analyses

Significant correlations emerged between disgust and interest toward insect-based food, and self-reported intention to buy and eat it. Because these correlations were observed for both the regular and insect-containing food conditions, we compared them across scenarios using z-tests for

independent correlations. The correlation between disgust and intention to buy the appreciated food (Table 1) differed significantly between conditions, $Z = 2.34, p = .019$, as did the correlation between disgust toward insect food and intention to buy the food associated with a disgusted reaction, $Z = 2.67, p = .008$. In contrast, correlations involving interest – both with intention to buy the appreciated food and the food associated with disgust – did not differ between conditions, $Z = 0.88, p = .377$ and $Z = 1.48, p = .138$, respectively.

Next, we examined whether participants' disgust and interest were related to the OEC effect. Differential BIAT and intention scores were computed as the difference between the positively and negatively paired biscuits, with higher values indicating a stronger OEC effect. These differential scores were uncorrelated with disgust and interest ratings (Table 3), suggesting that general disgust or interest toward insect-containing foods did not influence the OEC effect.

Table 3.

Experiment 1. Pearson's Correlations between the OEC Effect and Disgust/Interest Ratings

	Differential BIAT	Differential intention
<i>Regular biscuits</i>		
Disgust	-.03 [-.27, .21]	-.11 [-.34, .13]
Interest	-.01 [-.23, .25]	.09 [-.16, .32]
<i>Insect-containing biscuits</i>		
Disgust	-.05 [-.13, .22]	-.22 [†] [-.38, -.05]
Interest	.03 [-.20, .15]	.12 [-.06, .28]

Note. Values in brackets represent 95% confidence intervals. [†] $p < .10$, * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Discussion

Study 1 demonstrated that the OEC manipulation effectively shaped both attitudes (BIAT) and intentions toward biscuits. Participants consistently preferred the brand paired with appreciation over the brand paired with disgust, for both traditional biscuits (replicating Kasran et al., 2023) and novel insect-containing biscuits (extending prior findings). The effect was robust across food types and was independent of participants' general disgust or interest in insect-based foods.

Participants reporting stronger disgust toward insect ingredients showed lower purchase intentions to insect-containing biscuits, regardless of the model's reaction. Conversely, participants with higher interest in insect-based foods exhibited higher purchase intentions across both model pairings. These patterns align with the view that disgust functions as an aversive motivational signal promoting avoidance, whereas interest reflects approach motivation and curiosity toward novel foods (Piqueras-Fiszman et al., 2014; Stone et al., 2022). Importantly, differential OEC scores – reflecting the relative influence of the model's affective reaction – were uncorrelated with participants' self-reported disgust or interest, suggesting that general attitudes toward insect foods do not determine the magnitude of the social learning effect.

Participants' disgust toward insect-based foods, as measured by the EAQ, was negatively associated with their purchase intention even for regular biscuits. Although the EAQ specifically assesses reactions to insect-based foods, these can be related to a broader, trait-level disgust propensity: Individuals high in this propensity are generally more sensitive to potential contamination, more prone to food neophobia and selective eating (Brown et al., 2022; Egolf et al., 2018). Notably, the regular biscuit brands in this experiment were unfamiliar to participants, potentially eliciting cautious responses from individuals high in disgust sensitivity. This association supports prior findings that higher food-disgust sensitivity predicts selective eating, lower variety seeking, and avoidance of unfamiliar foods (Brown et al., 2022). Notably, the effect was stronger for insect-based biscuits, indicating that negative reactions were particularly relevant when insect ingredients were present. Crucially, neither disgust nor interest predicted the magnitude of the OEC effect, suggesting that social learning operated independently of preexisting disgust. The disgust measure was collected at the end of the experiment to avoid interfering with the manipulation; results should therefore be interpreted with caution.

Experiment 2

Overview

Experiment 2 examined whether OEC+ (observing a model eating the biscuit followed by a positive reaction) and VC (merely observing a model eating the biscuit) can shift preferences when the brands belong to separate categories that are evaluated differently. Specifically, we always compared attitudes towards an insect-based biscuit brand with attitudes towards a traditional biscuit (an inter-category comparison). For the traditional biscuit, the video merely showed a model holding the product. For the insect-based biscuit, we varied between participants whether the video showed the model holding the product (baseline), holding the product and eating the biscuit (VC), or holding the product, eating the biscuit and showing a positive reaction (OEC+). This allowed us to assess whether VC and OEC+ improved the attitude toward the insect-based biscuit relative to the attitude toward traditional biscuit.

This design represents a critical modification to Experiment 1, where the two brands belonged to the same category (either traditional biscuits, or biscuits with insects, manipulated between participants). Unlike the intra-category comparison of Experiment 1, where no prior preference existed between the two unknown brands, the current experiment requires the manipulation to act against a pre-existing cultural aversion to insect-based food. Modifying an existing negative reaction is inherently more challenging than merely creating a new preference (Albarracín & Shaivitt, 2018).

Participants and design

Three hundred sixteen participants (122 women, 190 men, three non-binary individuals, and one who preferred not to answer; $M_{age} = 30.43$ years, $SD = 7.45$) took part in the study. They were recruited via Prolific (<https://www.prolific.com/>) with the following inclusion criteria: age 18-45 and native Italian speakers, with a Prolific approval rate of at least 95%. These criteria were based on evidence that both age and cultural background influence acceptance of novel foods, including insect-based products (Laureati et al., 2024). This is particularly relevant in the present study, as we are comparing preferences across different food categories, unlike Experiment 1, which compared brands within the same category. Participants were compensated at the standard Prolific rate (£9 / \$12 per hour).

The number of participants was determined based on resource constraints, with a target sample of approximately 288 participants, as indicated by a sensitivity power analysis described below. To account for expected exclusions (see Results), we slightly increased the sample size to $N = 310$. Sensitivity power analyses were conducted using G*Power (Faul et al., 2007). With a significance level of $\alpha = .025$ (adjusted via Bonferroni correction for the two main dependent variables), a sample of 288 provides power $(1-\beta) = .90$ to detect an effect size of $f = 0.23$ and power $(1-\beta) = .95$ to detect an effect size of $f = 0.25$ in a between-participants ANOVA with one factor with three levels. For post hoc comparisons among the three conditions, considering Bonferroni correction ($\alpha = .05/6 = .008$) and directional hypotheses, this sample yields a sensitivity of Cohen's $d = 0.54$ with power $(1-\beta) = .90$ and Cohen's $d = 0.59$ with provides power $(1-\beta) = .95$, indicating sufficient power to detect medium-to-large effects. We considered this level of sensitivity appropriate for the study's objectives.

The experiment employed a between-subjects, single-factor design with three conditions: baseline, VC, and OEC+). Participants were randomly assigned to each condition (111 baseline, 98 VC, 107 OEC+). Attitudes toward insect-based versus regular food were measured using two dependent variables: a semantic differential scale and an IAT score.

Materials

Target products. The target products were the same biscuit brands as those in Experiment 1. In this study, Darivo was presented as an insect-based brand, and Medeva as a traditional biscuit brand.

Videos. The videos used in Experiment 1 were adapted for Experiment 2. For Medeva, the video showed the product packaging and the model presenting the biscuit, without any mention of insect ingredients. For Darivo, the video showed the packaging indicating the presence of insect derivatives and included the same initial part where the model showed the product. In the baseline condition, the video ended after the model displayed the package; in the VC condition, it ended after the model tasted the biscuit; in the OEC+ condition, the whole video was shown, as in Experiment 1.

Implicit Association Test. We assessed automatic reactions using the Implicit Association Test (IAT; Greenwald et al., 1998), to capture relative preferences between the two brands. We used

the iatgen implementation in Qualtrics (Carpenter et al., 2019). The two biscuit brands served as target categories, with the same images and taste-related adjectives used in Experiment 1. IAT D scores were computed using the built-in penalty procedure, following Greenwald, Nosek, and Banaji (2003). Positive scores indicate a preference for the insect-based brand, while negative scores indicate a preference for the regular brand; larger absolute values reflect a stronger preference. The reliability was good (Cronbach's $\alpha = .87$).

Semantic Differentials. We assessed self-reported attitudes as in Experiment 1. Scores were computed as the difference between the average ratings for the insect-based and regular biscuit brands, so that, analogous to the IAT scores, positive values indicated a preference for the insect-based brand and negative values indicated a preference for the regular brand. The reliability was excellent (Cronbach's $\alpha = .94$).

Disgust and interest toward eating insects. They were measured as in Experiment 1. As the correlation between the Interest and Disgust subscales was strongly negative, $r = -.83, p < .001$, indicating that higher disgust was associated with lower interest scores, following the preregistration, we computed an aggregated measure by averaging all the items, after reverse-coding interest items. Therefore, high values indicate a high level of disgust and a low level of interest toward food with insects. This aggregated measure demonstrated excellent reliability (Cronbach's $\alpha = .95$).

Manipulation check. Participants assigned to the VC condition were asked what was model did with the Darivo biscuits by selecting one of three options: “I don’t know”, “He did not do anything”, or “He ate them”. In the OEC+ condition they were asked what the model did after eating the Darivo biscuits by selecting one of four options: “Satisfied”, “Disgusted”, “None”, “I don’t remember”. No manipulation check questions were asked to participants in the baseline condition.

Knowledge of brands and SRSI. These were measured using the same procedures as in Experiment 1.

Compliance with demand characteristics. Participants indicated the extent to which they adapted their responses to meet our expectations on a scale from 1 (*Not at all*) to 5 (*A lot*).

Demographic questions. Participants reported their age, gender, proficiency in Italian, prior experience with insect-based food, and meat consumption. Meat consumption was assessed with the

question “Do your eating habits include meat (e.g., steaks, cold cuts) and/or foods that contain meat (e.g., pasta with bolognese sauce)?” with response options “Yes” or “No”.

Food Choice Questionnaire – Sensory Appeal Subscale (FCQ; Steptoe et al., 1995). For exploratory purposes, participants completed the four-item Sensory Appeal subscale, which assesses the importance of smell, taste, texture, and appearance in food. Responses were rated on a 5-point scale from 1 (*Not at all important*) to 5 (*Very important*). Correlations among the items were low (.09 to .33), and the scale overall reliability was poor ($\alpha = .39$), so it was excluded from further analysis. Importantly, no preregistered analyses involved this scale.

Procedure

After providing informed consent, participants completed the Disgust and Interest and Sensory Appeal scales. They were then shown a photo of the two biscuit brands, Medeva and Darivo, with text noting that the ingredients were nearly identical except that Darivo contained insect derivatives.

Participants then viewed two videos, each repeated three times for a total of six presentations, with order randomized between participants. The Medeva video was identical for all participants, showing only the model presenting the brand. The Darivo video varied between participants according to condition (baseline, VC, OEC+), as described above. Following the videos, participants in the VC and OEC+ conditions completed the manipulation check, with incorrect responses triggering a replay up to 2 times.

Finally, participants completed the IAT and semantic differentials in counterbalanced order, followed by questions on brand knowledge, demographics, compliance with demand characteristics, and the SRSI.

Hypotheses

We formulated three directional hypotheses:

H1: OEC+ would enhance preference for insect-containing food compared to baseline.

H2: VC would enhance preference for insect-containing food compared to baseline.

H3: OEC+ would produce a stronger effect than VC, resulting in more positive attitudes towards insect-based foods.

Results

All statistical analyses were performed in R. In addition to the packages used in the first study, the following R packages were employed: readxl (Wickham & Bryan, 2025), openxlsx (Schauberger & Walker, 2025), lme4 (Bates et al., 2015), rstatix (Kassambara, 2023), Hmisc (Harrell Jr, 2024), and insight (Lüdtke, Waggoner & Makowski, 2019).

Preliminary analyses

Following the preregistration, participants were excluded for the following reasons: negative response to the SRSI “use me” question ($n = 2$), excessive number of incorrect responses in the IAT task ($>25\%$; $n = 16$), not eating meat ($n = 5$), or prior knowledge of Darivo ($n = 2$). The final sample consisted of 90 participants in the baseline group, 101 in the VC group, and 100 in the OEC+ group. The main descriptive statistics and Pearson’s correlations between the variables are reported in Table 4. As shown in Table 5, semantic differential scores vary across conditions, whereas IAT scores are near zero and similar across all conditions.

Table 4.

Experiment 2: Descriptive Statistics and Correlations among Measures.

	M	SD	Min	Max	Correlations		
					1.	2.	3.
1. IAT	-0.08	0.48	-1.15	1.11			
	-0.62	1.11	-4.00	4.00	.33***		
2. Semantic Differential					[.23, .43]		
	2.87	1.03	1.00	5.00	-.31***	-.57***	
3. Disgust-interest composite					[-.41, -.20]	[-.64, -.49]	

Note. Values in brackets represent 95% confidence intervals. [†] $p < .10$, * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Table 5.

Experiment 2: Mean IAT and Semantic Differential scores (SDs in parentheses) by Experimental Condition.

	IAT	Semantic Differential
Baseline	-0.10 (0.48)	-0.92 (1.16)
VC	-0.07 (0.48)	-0.47 (0.83)
OEC+	-0.08 (0.47)	-0.42 (1.21)

Preregistered Analyses

Two parallel ANCOVAs were conducted on IAT and Semantic Differential scores, with experimental condition as the independent variable and the disgust-interest score as a covariate.

The ANCOVA on the Semantic Differential showed a significant effect of condition, $F(2,289) = 8.948, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .059, 95\% \text{ CI } [.020, 1.000]$, with a significant effect of the covariate, $F(1,287) = 138.890, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .326, 95\% \text{ CI } [.256, 1.000]$. Inspection of the regression coefficients indicated that higher disgust-interest scores were associated with lower preference for the insect-containing biscuits, $\beta = -0.605, p < .001$, consistent with the expected direction of the covariate. Consistent with preregistered hypotheses, one-tailed *t*-tests for independent samples indicated that both OEC+ (H1) and VC (H2) increased preference for the insect-containing biscuits relative to baseline and both strategies led to a substantial reduction of the preference for the regular biscuit brand compared to the baseline, diminishing it by almost half a standard deviation (see Table 6). However, OEC+ did not outperform VC (H3), as the difference between the two strategies was negligible and non-significant.

Table 6.

*Experiment 2: One-tailed Independent Sample *t*-tests Comparing Semantic Differential Scores across Experimental Conditions.*

	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>Cohen's d</i>
Baseline vs. VC	3.110	181.17	.001	0.447
				[0.161, 0.731]
Baseline vs. OEC+	2.867	199	.002	0.404

				[0.125, 0.683]
VC vs. OEC+	0.191	188	.424	0.028
				[-0.257, 0.313]

Note. For the Baseline vs. VC comparison, the Welch test was computed due to heteroskedasticity. Values in brackets represent 95% confidence intervals.

For the IAT, the ANCOVA revealed no significant effect of condition, $F(2,287) = 0.154, p = .858, \eta^2_p < .001, 95\% \text{ CI } [.000, 1.000]$, while the disgust-interest covariate was significant, $F(1,287) = 29.842, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .094, 95\% \text{ CI } [.047, 1.000]$. The direction of the relationship between the covariate and the preference for insect food was negative, as expected, $\beta = -0.143, p < .001$.

Following the preregistration of specific hypotheses, one-sided t-tests were conducted to examine differences between conditions in the IAT. The results indicate that none of our hypotheses were supported, for all t-tests $|t| < 0.51, p > .30$.

Ancillary Analyses

Two ancillary ANCOVAs were conducted to test whether disgust-interest moderated the effect of the experimental manipulation on both implicit (IAT) and explicit (Semantic Differential) evaluations of the insect-based biscuits. In the analysis of IAT scores, neither the main effect of condition, $F(2,285) = 0.154, p = .857, \eta^2_p = .001, 95\% \text{ CI } [.000, 1.000]$ nor the condition \times disgust-interest interaction, $F(2,285) = 1.112, p = .330, \eta^2_p = .008, 95\% \text{ CI } [.000, 1.000]$, was statistically significant. The main effect of the covariate remained significant, $F(1,285) = 29.865, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .095, 95\% \text{ CI } [.048, 1.000]$.

The ANCOVA on Semantic Differential ratings replicated the significant main effects of both the conditions, $F(2,285) = 9.069, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .060, 95\% \text{ CI } [.020, 1.000]$, and disgust-interest, $F(1,285) = 140.766, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .331, 95\% \text{ CI } [.260, 1.000]$. The condition \times disgust-interest interaction did not reach statistical significance, $F(2,285) = 2.940, p = .054, \eta^2_p = .020, 95\% \text{ CI } [.000, 1.000]$.

Discussion

The OEC and VC procedures influenced self-reported preferences, even when the two target foods belonged to categories that differed in their consumers' acceptance. Exposure to the social-

learning videos substantially reduced the magnitude of the preference for the traditional food, although it did not eliminate it. The effect was comparable for OEC and VC, indicating that adding positive emotive reactions did not enhance the impact of witnessing food consumption. In contrast, no significant changes emerged for spontaneous preferences. Consistent with Experiment 1, disgust toward insect food was negatively associated with preferences for insect-containing foods across both outcome measures. Higher disgust predicted lower preferences on both the IAT and the semantic differential, and, as before, it did not significantly moderate the effect of the social learning manipulation.

General Discussion

This research investigated whether two social learning procedures, OEC and VC, could be effective for promoting acceptance of insect-based foods, a category that elicits cultural aversion among Western consumers. We found that these learning procedures influenced participants' reactions to regular foods and to those containing insect derivatives.

Differences Between Experiments and Implications for Interpretation

In Experiment 1, effects were observed in direct (self-report) and indirect measures, whereas in Experiment 2, effects were limited to direct measures. A theoretically relevant distinction between the two experiments concerns the type of social learning manipulation. In Experiment 1, participants observed both positive (appreciation) and negative (disgust) reactions to the foods, whereas in Experiment 2, the strategies focused on improving attitudes by showing positive or neutral reactions. Observing negative reactions may exert a stronger influence than observing positive reactions, consistent with the negativity bias (Baumeister et al., 2001; van den Bosch et al., 2015), which may explain why the effects in Experiment 1 were more robust and detectable across measures. Another difference between the two experiments is that the manipulation in Experiment 1 may have created a more pronounced contrast between the two brands: One brand was paired with a positive social signal, the other with a negative one. In Experiment 2, by contrast, one brand was accompanied by the

positive social signal and the other by a neutral presentation. The contrast context of Experiment 1 may have amplified the impact of the manipulation (Bar-Anan & Dahan, 2013).

Finally, the learning contexts differed. In Experiment 1, participants formed preferences between two novel brands within the same product category, creating a context conducive to attitude formation, as there were no strong preexisting preferences. In Experiment 2, participants compared a novel insect-containing brand with a novel non-insect brand. Although both brands were unfamiliar, the difference in ingredients likely activated preexisting attitudes toward insect-based foods, placing participants in a context of attitude change. Because existing attitudes are resistant to change (Albarracín & Shaivitt, 2018), this difference in context may be part of the explanation of why the effects observed in Experiment 1 were more robust and evident across measures, whereas in Experiment 2 they emerged only in self-reports.

Interpreting the Lack of Differences Between OEC+ and VC

Unexpectedly, in Experiment 2 we found no differences between the effects of OEC+ and VC. This result suggests that observing a model consume the food may already convey positive information, rendering additional positive signals redundant. From the propositional perspective, the model's eating signals that the food is safe, palatable, or socially acceptable, so that the model's positive reaction adds little new information. Similarly, from an associative perspective, both OEC+ and VC procedures paired the insect-containing food with the eating behavior, which is evaluated positively (Zogmaister, Brignoli, et al., 2023) and, therefore, serves as positive unconditioned stimulus; in this context, any additional emotional reaction by the model may provide little extra reinforcement. However, a single study is not sufficient to rule out the possibility of differences between OEC+ and VC. The takeaway from this study is that both procedures are effective in producing improvements in attitudes toward the target food.

No impact of disgust toward insect food on the size of attitude change

Across both studies, self-reported disgust toward insect-containing foods predicted more negative evaluations of these products, confirming the robustness of this association. However,

disgust was not significantly associated with the effect of the social learning manipulations in either study. This effect, together with the absence of interactions between the manipulation and the type of food in Experiment 1, suggests that the observed attitude change operated independently of pre-existing affective dispositions. Nevertheless, the absence of a significant interaction should be interpreted cautiously. Failing to detect an effect does not constitute evidence of its absence. Future studies, with a fine-grained assessment of disgust (e.g., a scale measuring disgust for foods containing insect derivatives), may help clarify whether and under what conditions disgust attenuates or amplifies the impact of social learning on attitudes toward insect-based foods.

This absence of moderation by disgust contrasts with evidence that appetitive motivational states such as hunger and thirst can amplify the effects of approach–avoidance training on implicit preferences: Zogmaister and colleagues (2016) found that deprivation-related states strengthen the formation of implicit preferences following repeated approach/avoidance behaviors, whereas moderation was weaker or absent for explicit evaluations. The present findings suggest that different motivational and affective states may play distinct roles in shaping evaluative learning. Whereas homeostatic drives such as hunger enhance approach-related learning, disgust—despite being robustly associated with negative evaluations—does not appear to attenuate the impact of observational social information. It is, however, important to notice the presence of differences between learning driven by one’s own actions, as in Zogmaister et al.’s (2016) studies, and learning from observing others’ behavior, as in the present research. Accordingly, our results suggest new research directions that explore the distinction between first-person and vicarious experiences and the influence of different types of motivational states on social learning.

Practical implications

The present findings offer several practical insights beyond the general conclusion that OEC+ and VC increase acceptance of insect-based foods. First, the observed social learning effects were elicited through brief video stimuli (approximately 15 seconds), highlighting the scalability of this approach. Such short-format content is well-suited for dissemination via social media, online advertising, or public awareness campaigns, enabling a broad reach at a relatively low cost. Its brevity

also facilitates repeated exposure and integration into everyday media consumption, potentially enhancing cumulative impact.

Second, the applicability of these strategies is not limited to insect-based products. The underlying mechanism of observational social learning can be plausibly extended to a wide range of novel, unfamiliar, or culturally stigmatized foods, including under-consumed vegetables and emerging protein alternatives, such as plant-based or cultured meat products. From both a public health and a sustainability perspective, this suggests a flexible, low-cost approach for promoting more diverse and environmentally sustainable dietary patterns.

Recent findings by Kasran and colleagues (2022, 2023; see also Zogmaister, Vezzoli, et al., 2023) highlight that the effectiveness of observational learning depends on the perceived authenticity of the model's reaction. To ensure observers draw the intended inferences (e.g., that the food is safe, palatable, or socially acceptable), the model must be perceived as credible and sincere. Campaigns should therefore prioritize socially relevant and trustworthy models, and design scenarios that engage viewers' attention and inferential processing rather than relying on passive exposure.

Finally, observational strategies can be integrated into educational and training contexts, such as schools or community-based programs that promote healthy eating. Showing not only factual information but also the act of consumption may foster more positive and informed attitudes toward unfamiliar or initially aversive foods.

Limitations and emerging questions

All participants were Italian, a population with strong culinary traditions and low baseline acceptance of insect-based foods (Arena et al., 2020; Verneau et al., 2016; 2020). This may have influenced initial attitudes; however, it underscores the robustness of the observed effects: Even in a culturally resistant context, both OEC+ and VC increased acceptance of the target foods. The focus on insect-based foods also limits generalizability, since Western consumers' aversion often reflects cultural unfamiliarity rather than sensory properties. Similar initial aversions are observed for other novel or culturally uncommon foods, such as organ meats or emerging protein sources, including

cultured meat (Laureati et al., 2024). Further research with different populations and foods is needed to confirm the scope and boundary conditions of these social learning strategies. Additionally, this research investigated taste-related aspects of the food evaluations, and future studies could examine whether these interventions also influence other product perceptions, like perceived healthiness, usefulness, or sustainability. Future research should also investigate the impact of these procedures on behavior (e.g., actual consumption of these foods) beyond attitudinal or intention measures.

Another limitation concerns the absence of implicit effects in Study 2. Although the manipulation was strong enough to create explicit preferences between two insect-based brands, a single modeling episode may have been insufficient to influence automatic reactions. Future studies could examine whether repeated, temporally spaced exposures strengthen the impact of the manipulations, potentially revealing effects on spontaneous behavioral responses.

Overall, while a single contribution cannot answer all questions about the effectiveness and boundary conditions of observational social learning, the present work provides evidence for these mechanisms in a challenging context and highlights multiple promising directions for future research. Far from being a limitation, the open questions uncovered here represent a strength, pointing to rich avenues for extending our understanding of how social learning shapes attitudes toward novel or culturally unfamiliar foods.

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